

ISic1518

I.Sicily inscription 1518

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14599

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ε]νταῦθα κῆται ὁ
2. μακαρίας μνήμης
3. [Α]γάθων χρηστὸς κ(αὶ)
4. [ἄ]μενπτος διελθῶν
5. [τὸ]ν βίον ἀπετέθη τῇ
6. [πρ]ὸ ἰγ καλ(ανδῶν) Ἀπριλίων

Apparatus

Text after Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645018

Bibliography

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.22
Orsi, P. 1895. Insigne epigrafe del cimitero di S. Giovanni in Siracusa. *Römische
Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 9:
299-308. At 493 no.188

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